

Identification and description of ornamental plants and trees at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo

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Received: October 4, 2023; Accepted: December 19, 2023 ; Published: March 17, 2024

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10827738

Abstract: A field survey was conducted in 2023 to identify and describe the ornamental plants and trees species within the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo. Plant samples were taken from around 20 buildings, landscaped with ornamental plants and tree species in four locations of UAES between the months of June and August 2023. In each location, the ornamental plants and trees species were captured and immediately identified with the aid of a phone App (Google lens) in an android phone (Nokia 2.4). Leaf and flower samples were also taken to the herbarium for further identification with the aid of reference book and botanical keys. The results showed that a total of 53 general of ornamental plants and tree species belonging to 34 families were identified and described. Plants from the Euphorbaceae family had the highest number of species. Indoor plants were only found within the senate and administrative buildings. This study would be useful to ornamental plant fanciers, growers and florists.

Keywords: *Google lens, landscaping, flowers, aesthetic values, floriculture*

Introduction

Floriculture is an aspect of horticulture that involves the cultivation, management and sales of ornamental plants and trees (Sani *et al.*, 2016). Ornamental plants are those plants that are cultivated for the purpose of increasing the beauty of the gardens, lawns, houses and other establishments. They come

in form of trees, shrubs, climbers, grasses, palms and bamboos (Chen, 2021). Majority of them are used for aesthetic and landscaping purposes due to their conspicuous and beautiful flowers or variegated leaves or stems (Chen, 2021). In the world of agriculture, floriculture is on the increase and fast growing. Take for

instance, in In the United States of America, sales and production of ornamental plants represent the 6th largest agricultural commodity group, in which their sales alone generated revenue worth 4.6 billion in 2018 (USDA, 2019). Their productions are also on the increase in Europe, China, Columbia, Ecuador, Brazil and Africa (Ethiopia and Kenya) (Volckaert, 2014; Boehm, 2018). Just like other plants, they are important in conserving and protecting of the environment. They are important source of wind break system, they are involved in the purification and removal of certain toxins and greenhouse gasses from the atmosphere (Adeoye *et al.*, 2014; Koriesh, 2020). Recently, studies have shown that many of them can be medicinal and pesticidal (Adekunle and Akinlua, 2007; Vieira *et al.*, 2020). Ornamental trees provide shades for relaxation and shelter during light rains and solar radiation (Sani *et al.*, 2016). However, despite their importance to man and the environment, there is a sharp neglect of floriculture by researchers in Nigeria, and also their demands by ornamental fanciers are low. This is partly due to low awareness of their importance, lack of interest in their studies and poor knowledge in their identity. Hence, selection, description and identification of several species of these plants are becoming difficult and problematic. The names, particularly the scientific and English names of many of

these plants and trees species are not known and as such local florists depend on local names for their identification. Hence, the objective of this study was to identify and describe common ornamental plants and tree species within the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo Nigeria.

Material and Method

Study area

A survey study was conducted at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo, located on latitude 05° 18' 26'' N, and longitude 06° 56' 37'' E at 152 m above sea level, in the tropical rain-forest zone of Nigeria. The area has a mean annual rainfall of about 2200 mm and a mean daily temperature of about 28°C. The soil of the area is of the order, Ultisol according to the USDA soil taxonomy with the parent material as the coastal plain sands (Nigeria Meteorological Agency, 2015).

Sampling, identification and classification procedures

Samples of ornamental plant were taken from about 20 buildings landscaped with a number of ornamental plants and tree species in five locations of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo between the months of July and August 2023. The locations were

school entrance, Senate building (Administrative building, Examination division, ICT I, II and III buildings and entrepreneurship center), Love garden (Student Affairs Building and Hostel and Staff Quarters), major roads and Faculty Buildings. In each location, the ornamental plants and tree species were captured and identified with a phone App (Google lens) in an android phone (Nokia 2.4). Plant samples consisting leaves and flowers or cones were taken from each plant sampled with the aid of a pen knife from each location. They were placed on a plant press and taken to the Department of Biological Sciences and Crop Science for further processing and identification to genus level. The plants were named and classified based on leaves, floral, uses and mode of propagation with the aid of a manual containing major genera of tropical flowering plants by (Llamas, 2003).

Results and Discussion

A total of 53 genera of ornamental plants and tree species of 34 families were identified within the UAES, Umuagwo, Nigeria (Table 1). Plants from the Euphorbaceae family had the highest number (6) of plant species. A variety of ornamental plants and trees were sampled and identified within the entrance of the institution (Table 2). Plants belonging to the

family Euphorbiaceae including *C. variegatum*, *A. wilkisia* and *H. creptans* were the most predominant plant species identified at the institution's entrance. *Duranta repens*, *D. erecta*, *R. sinensis* (red), *R. sinensis* (variegated), *I. coccinea*, *F. altissima*, *H. puniceum*, *T. occidentalis* and *E. arvense* were also identified within this premises. The tree species found in this part of the institution are *A. indica*, *M. indica*, *T. catappa*, *E. guinensis*, *H. creptans* and *G. gmelina*. A number of these plants and tree were used to landscape and beautify the buildings and roads within the institution. Twenty three outdoor ornamental plants, 23 tree species and seven indoor / potted ornamental plants were seen growing in the institution. The most dominant ornamental plant species were *I. coccinea* (Ixora jungle flame), *Duranta* spp. (Sky flower), *F. altissima* (council tree), *Acalypha* spp. (Copperleaf) *T. catappa* (Umbrella tree), *M. indica* (Mango tree) and Hibiscus spp. These plants were found in virtually all the locations visited. Many of them are being used as hedges, pathways to offices, avenue plants and potted plants. At the entrance of the school, a number of outdoor ornamental plants were planted in such a way that they overlapped each other, from one end to the other end of the school's entrance, giving that premises a pleasant sight to behold.

Thirteen genera of ornamental plant species including *D. repens*, *T. peruviana*, *I. coccinea*, *F. altissima*, *D. erecta* (variegated), *D. erecta* (Gold), *R. sinensis* (hybrids), *R. sinensis* (kermessinus), *A. wilkisiama* (copperleaf wine), *A. wilkisiama* (copperleaf green), *E. arvense*, *H. bourgaeana* and *F. altissima* were identified within the senate and administrative buildings of the institution (Table 3). Seven potted plants including *E. cupreata*, *A. commutatum*, *P. scutellaria*, *S. trifasciata*, *J. podagrica*, *C. oshimensis*, *C. asparagus*, *E. ammak* were all found within this premises. *Irvingia gabonensis*, *C. sinensis*, *P. acutifolia*, *E. guineensis*, *L. leucocephala*, *C. nucifera*, *P. dulcis*, *P. dactylifera*, *A. indica*, *C. papaya*, *M. indica*, *T. catappa* and *P. macrophylla* were the major trees identified within this premises. The indoor plants were basically found only around the senate building where they were planted in pots and placed on strategic positions within the senate building.

Table 1: Ornamental plants and trees, identified at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo

Family	Species	Total
Areaceae	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i> , <i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> , <i>Cocos nucifera</i> , <i>Archontophoenix alexandrae</i>	4
Combretaceae	<i>Terminalia catappa</i> and <i>Plumeria acutifolia</i>	2
Irvingiaceae	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	1
Euphorbaceae	<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i> , <i>Acalypha wilkisiama</i> , <i>Hura creptans</i> , <i>Euphobia ammak</i> , <i>Jatropha integerrima</i> and <i>Jatropha podagrica</i>	6
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta erecta</i> (Gold)	3
Cuperessaceae	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	1
Rubiaceae	<i>Ixora coccinea</i> and <i>Hamelia patens</i>	2
Moraceae	<i>Ficus altissima</i>	1
Agaveceae	<i>Agave americana</i>	1
Amaryllidaceae	<i>Hippeastrum puniceum</i>	1
Malvaceae	<i>Rosa-sinensis</i> hybrids and <i>Rosa sinensis</i> var: kermessinus	2
Equisetuaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	1
Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	1
Anacardiaceae	<i>Magnifera indica</i>	1
Lamiaceae	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> and <i>Tectona grandis</i>	2
Apocynaceae	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i> and <i>Allamanda cathartica</i>	2
Heliconiaceae	<i>Heliconia bourgaeana</i>	1
Gesneriaceae	<i>Episcia cupreata</i>	1
Araceae	<i>Aglaonema commutatum</i> and <i>caladium bicolor</i>	2
Araliaceae	<i>Polyscias scutellaria</i>	1
Asparagaceae	<i>Sansevieria trifasciata</i> and <i>Cordyline asparagus</i>	2

Myrtaceae	<i>Eugenia uniflora</i>	1
Gramineae	<i>Carex oshimensis</i>	1
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	1
Bromliaceae	<i>Ananas comosus</i>	1
	<i>Leucaena leucocephala, Delonix regia and Pentaclethra macrophylla</i>	3
Fabaceae	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	1
Rosaceae	<i>Carica papaya</i>	1
Caricaceae	<i>Philodendron hederaceum</i>	1
Araceae	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	1
Annooaceae	<i>Annona muricata</i>	1
Annonaceae	<i>Pseuderanthemum stainless</i>	1
Acanthaceae	<i>Pinus densiflora</i>	1
Pinaceae	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	1
Moringaceae		
Total		53

Table 2: Ornamental plants identified at the entrance of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo

Family name	Scientific name	English name	Common name
Ornamental plants			
Euphorbaceae	<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i>	Croton luganda Golden dew drop, sky	Rush foil
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta repens</i>	flowers	Yellow bush
Cuperessaceae	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	Thuja plicata	Red cedar
		Scarlet or Ixora Jungle	
Rubiaceae	<i>Ixora coccinea</i>	Flame	Flame of the wood
Moraceae	<i>Ficus altissima</i>	Counsel tree, lofty wig	Yellow ficus
		Golden dew drop, sky	
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta erecta</i>	flowers	Yellow bush
Euphorbaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkisia</i>	Copperleaf (green)	Acalypha
Malvaceae	<i>Rosa-sinensis</i> hybrids	Hibiscus (Red)	Chinese hibiscus
Amaryllidaceae	<i>Hippeastrum puniceum</i>	Barbados lily	Lis rouge
Malvaceae	<i>Rosa Sinensis</i>	Hibiscus (variegated)	Chinese hibiscus
Rubiaceae	<i>Hamelia patens</i>	Texas firebush, red head	Scarlet bush
Euphorbaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkisia</i>	Copperleaf (wine)	Acalypha
Equisetuaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	Horsetail	Scouring rush
Trees species			
Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem tree	Margosa
Anacardiaceae	<i>Magnifera indica</i>	Mango	Mango
Combretaceae	<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	Umbrella tree, step tree	India almond
Arecaceae	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	African oil palm	African oil palm
			Possumwood, Monkey
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Hura crepttans</i>	sand-box	no climb
Lamiaceae	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Beechwood	Gmelina

Table 3: Ornamental plants identified at the Senate and Administrative Buildings at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo

Family name	Scientific name	English name	Common name
Ornamental plants			
		Golden dew drop, sky	
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta repens</i>	flowers	Yellow bush
Cuperessaceae	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	Thuja plicata	Red cedar

Apocynaceae	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	Yellow oleander Lucky-nut Scarlet or Ixora Jungle	Cascabel
Rubiaceae	<i>Ixora coccinea</i>	Flame	Flame of the wood
Moraceae	<i>Ficus altissima</i>	Counsel tree, Lofty fig Golden dew drop, sky flowers	Yellow ficus Yellow bush
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta erecta</i>	Golden dew drop, sky flowers	Yellow bush
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta erecta</i>	flowers	Yellow bush
Malvaceae	<i>Rosa-sinensis</i> hybrids <i>Rosa-sinensis</i> var: kermessinus	Hibiscus (red) Hibiscus (variegated leaves)	Chinese hibiscus Chinese hibiscus
Malvaceae			Chinese hibiscus
Euphorbaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkisiama</i>	Copperleaf (wine)	Acalypha
Euphorbaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkisiama</i>	Copperleaf (green)	Acalypha
Equisetuaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	Horsetail	Scouring rush Lobster claws, wild plantain
Heliconiaceae	<i>Heliconia bourgaeana</i>	Bird paradise	
Indoor plants			
Euphorbaceae	<i>Euphorbia ammak</i>	Candelabra spurge Carpet-plant or flame-violet,	African candelabra Tiger stripe
Gesneriaceae	<i>Episcia cupreata</i>		
Araceae	<i>Aglaonema commutatum</i>	Painted drop-tongue	Chinese evergreen
Araliaceae	<i>Polyscias scutellaria</i>	Shield aralia	Plum aralia
Asparagaceae	<i>Sansevieria trifasciata</i>	Snake plant	Mother-in-law's tongue
Euphorbaceae	<i>Jatropha podagrica</i>	Bottle plant or gout plant	Buddha belly plant,
Cyperaceae	<i>Carex oshimensis</i>	Japanese sedge	Evergold
Asparagaceae	<i>Cordyline asparagus</i>	Cabbage palm	Good luck plant, palm lily
Tree / shrubs			
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Orange	Orange
Combretaceae	<i>Plumeria acutifolia</i>	Frangipani tree	Red-jasmine or temple tree
Arecaceae	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	African oil palm	African oil palm Lead tree, <i>Leucaena</i> ,
Fabaceae	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	River tamarind	Jumbie Bean,
Annonaceae	<i>Annona muricata</i>	Guanabana	Graviola
Arecaceae	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Coconut	Coco
Rosaceae	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Almond tree	Fruit tree
Arecaceae	<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	Date-palm	Palma datilera
Irvingiaceae	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	African mango	Bush mango
† Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem tree	Margosa
Caricaceae	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Pawpaw	Pawpaw
Anacardiaceae	<i>Magnifera indica</i>	Mango	Mango
Combretaceae	<i>Terminalia catappa</i> <i>Pentaclethra</i>	Umbrella tree, step tree	India almond
Fabaceae	<i>macrophylla</i>	African oil bean	Ugba or Ukpaka

Nine general of ornamental plants and six general of trees species were identified within the love garden premises (Table 4). The ornamental plants were *D. repens*, *I. coccinea*, *R. Sinensis*, *A. wilkisiama*, *A. wilkisiama*, *A. cathartica*, *F. altissima*, *P. hederaceum* and *E. uniflora* while the tree species were; *T. catappa*, *A. alexandrae*, *D.*

regia, *P. macrophylla*, *G. arborea* and *P. longifolia*.

A total of eighteen genera of ornamental plants were sampled and identified in all the faculties within the institution and these plants were *D. repens*, *D. erecta* (variegated), *L. palustris*, *D. erecta* (Gold) *A. wilkisiama* (copperleaf green), *A.*

wilkisiana (copperleaf wine), *F. altissima*, *R. Sinensis* (red), *R. Sinensis* (variegated), *J. integerrima*, *E. arvense*, *T. peruviana*, *I. coccinea*

P. stainless, *A. americana*, *A. cathartica*, *F. altissima* and *P. densiflora* (Table 5). The trees identified were: *T. catappa*, *M. oleifera*, *M. indica*, *E. guineensis*, *P. dulcis*, *P. longifolia*, *A. indica*, *P. densiflora* and *A. comosus*.

Fourteen genera of tree species were identified along the major roads within the institution (Table 6). The trees species include: *T. catappa*, *D. regia*, *P. acutifolia*, *P. macrophylla*, *E. guineensis*, *G. arborea*, *H. creptans*, *C. japonica*, *T. grandis*, *P. dulcis*, *A. indica*, *P. longifolia*, *I. gabonensis* and *P. densiflora*

The ornamental plant species identified within the institution were either used as hedge, screen, avenue, focal, orchard, plantation, food, shade, indoor / potted or bordure plants. Majority of them are being used for making hedges while the least of them are being used for covering fences (climbers) and bordure plants (Table 7). Almost all the ornamental plants grown at the study area were the types that could be easily grown by stem cuttings (*I. coccinea*, *F. altissima*, *Acalypha* spp.) while fewer number of them could be grown by seeds (*C. oshimensis*), rhizomes (*H. bourgaeana*), corms (*C. bicolor*), bulbs (*H. puniceum*), stolon (*E. cupreata*), suckers (*S. trifasciata*

and *A. comosus*) and spores (*E. arvense*). Majority of the tree species were those types that could be cultivated by seeds while fewer number of them could be cultivated either by seeds or vegetatively (budding and grafting). Others including; *M. oleifera*, *L. leucocephala*, *P. acutifolia*, *P. densiflora* and *A. indica* could be cultivated by seeds or cuttings. Majority of the ornamental plants have their source of aesthetic values on their brightly and conspicuous colourfull flowers, while others such as *C. variegatum*, *Acalypha* species have theirs on broad variegated leaves. *Thuja occidentalis* (*Thuja plicata*) and *E. arvense* (Horsetail) had their aesthetic values mainly on their triangular and tail or tubular shapes respectively. Three plantations (*E. guineensis*, *P. macrophylla* and *I. gabonensis*) and two orchards (*A. comosus* and *A. muricata*) were seen in the institution (Table 8). They are basically planted for income generation and recreation purposes.

Most of the trees species including *D. regia* (Flame of the forest), *H. creptans* (Sandbox tree), *T. catappa* (Umbrella tree), *E. guineensis* (African Oil palm tree) and *G. arborea* (Beechwood) are being used as avenue plants. They were basically lined up on major roads of the institution. *Terminalia catappa*, *A. indica* (neem tree), *Cocos nucifera* (coconut tree) and *I. gabonensis* (bush mango) were seen planted on various buildings to serve as shades for visitors,

staff and students. Fruit trees including *M. indica* (Mango), *P. dulcis* (Almond), *C. papaya* (Pawpaw) were found scattered on the school premises, particularly around Faculties and Hostel premises. Other trees species such as *P. acutifolia* (temple tree) and *P. dactylifera* (Date-palm) were used to beautify most Faculties. The findings of the study agree with those of Sani *et al.* (2016) who conducted a survey to Identify and describe the ornamental plants and trees grown at the Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria. Their results showed that 68 plant species that included 27 ornamental plants (indoor plants), 16 shading plants (trees), 22 hedge plants (outdoor) and three lawn species were identified in the institution. *Ixora coccinea*, *Duranta* spp., *Acalypha* spp., *D. regia*, *T. occidentalis* amongst others were the common ornamental plants and trees species identified in their study.

In this present study, variations were observed among plants of the same species. Take for instance, two types of *D. erecta* were observed, one with green variegated leaves and the other with golden un-variegated leaves. Two *Rosa- sinensis* were also encountered one is characterized with green variegated leaves and the other with green un-variegated leaves. A wide variety of variations were observed among *Acalypha* species in terms of leaf colour ranging from wine and variegated colours.

Similar observation was made by Osawaru *et al.* (2014) who observed variations amongst ornamental plant species including *Rosa- sinensis* and *Acalypha* species.

Plantations and orchards were planted in some strategic arrears in the institution, apart from income generation and recreation purposes, these plantations and orchards further enhanced the aesthetic aspect of the institution.

The flower colours, mode of propagation and their uses mentioned in this study are not different from the reports of earlier workers (Oloyede *et al.*, 2008; Ochekwu *et al.*, 2022).

The benefits of ornamental plants and trees to man and the environment cannot be over emphasized as this has been reported to enhance the aesthetic value of a place. They produce fragrance smells and give directions to places and buildings when used as pathways (Sani *et al.*, 2016). They help in removing bad smells and toxic substances from the atmosphere and more importantly in reducing the concentration of carbon (IV) oxide in the atmosphere thereby reducing the effects of global warming (Adeoye *et al.*, 2014; Koriesh, 2020). *Ficus* spp., *Sansevieria* spp., *Aglaonema* spp., *Phoenix dactylifera* (Date Palm) and *Philodendron* spp. are among plants known for their special abilities to purify the air as well as removing formaldehyde, benzene, carbon monoxide and other toxins from the

atmosphere (Tra *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, they serve as windbreaks, helping to reduce wind intensity and at the same time protecting buildings from collapsing during heavy or high wind intensity (Adeoye *et al.*, 2014). Like other plants, ornamental plants and trees help in reducing water run off which in turn reduce soil erosion. Some of them possess antimicrobial substances and

as such are used traditionally in the treatment and management of various ailments (Osawaru *et al.*, 2014; Vieira *et al.*, 2020). Some contain pesticidal substances; hence can be used in controlling plant pests and diseases (Adekunle and Akinlua, 2007). Some of the trees species identified within the school were deliberately planted to provide shades for students and staff to relax during sunny days and light rains.

Table 4: Ornamental plants identified at the love garden of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo

Family name	Scientific name	English name	Common name
Ornamental plants			
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta repens</i>	Golden dew drop, sky flowers	Yellow bush
Rubiaceae	<i>Ixora coccinea</i>	Scarlet or Ixora	Flame of the wood
Malvaceae	<i>Rosa Sinensis</i>	Hibiscus	Chinese hibiscus
Euphorbaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkisia</i>	Copperleaf (wine)	Acalypha
Euphorbaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkisia</i>	Copperleaf (green)	Acalypha
Myrtaceae	<i>Eugenia uniflora</i>	Suriname cherry	Pitanga
Apocynaceae	<i>Allamanda cathartica</i>	Golden trumpet	Trumpetvine, yellow Allamanda
Moraceae	<i>Ficus altissima</i>	Council tree, lofty fig	Yellow ficus
Araceae	<i>Philodendron hederaceum</i>	Brazil	Heart leaf
Tree			
Combretaceae	<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	Umbrella tree, step tree	India almond
Arecaceae	<i>Archontophoenix alexandrae</i>	African oil bean	Ugba, Ukpaka
Fabaceae	<i>Delonix regia</i>	Flame of the forest	Bark cloth tree
Fabaceae.	<i>Pentaclethra macrophylla</i>	African oil bean	Ugba, Ukpaka
Lamiaceae	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Beechwood	Gmelina
Annooaceae	<i>Pllyalthia longifolia</i>	Masquerade	Police, False ashoka tree

Table 5: Ornamental plants identified among Faculties in the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo

Family name	Scientific name	English name	Common name
Ornamental plants			
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta repens</i>	Golden dewdrop, sky flowers	Yellow bush
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta erecta</i>	Golden dewdrop, sky flower	Yellow bush
Rubiaceae	<i>Hamelia patens</i>	Texas Firebush, red head	Scarlet bush
Verbanaceae	<i>Duranta erecta</i> (Gold)	Golden dewdrop or sky flower	Yellow bush
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkisia</i>	Copperleaf (wine)	Acalypha
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkisia</i>	Copperleaf (green)	Acalypha
Myrtaceae	<i>Eugenia uniflora</i>	Suriname cherry	Pitanga
Moraceae	<i>Ficus altissima</i>	Council tree, lofty fig	Yellow ficus
Malvaceae	<i>Rosa Sinensis</i>	Hibiscus	Chinese hibiscus
Malvaceae	<i>Rosa Sinensis</i>	Hibiscus (Variegated)	Chinese hibiscus
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Jatropha integerrima</i>	Peregrina	Spicy jatropa
Equisetuaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	Horsetail	Scouring rush
Apocynaceae	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	Yellow oleander, Lucky-nut	Cascabel
Rubiaceae	<i>Ixora coccinea</i>	Ixora Jungle Flame	flame of the woods
Arecaceae	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	African oil palm	African oil palm
Acanthaceae	<i>Pseuderanthemum stainless</i>	Stainless steel	Stainless steel
Agaveceae	<i>Agave americana</i>	Century plant	American aloe
Apocynaceae	<i>Allamanda cathartica</i>	Golden trumpet	Trumpetvine, yellow Allamanda
Tree species			
Combretaceae	<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	Umbrella tree, Step tree	India almond
Moringaceae	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	horseradish tree	Drumstick tree
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus densiflora</i>	Pinus	Japanese red pine
Anacardiaceae	<i>Magnifera indica</i>	Mango	Mango
Bromliaceae	<i>Ananas comosus</i>	Pineapple	Pineapple
Arecaceae	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	African oil palm	African oil palm
Rosaceae	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Almond	Fruit
Annoonaceae	<i>Plyalthia longifolia</i>	Masquerade	Police, False ashoka tree
Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem tree	Margosa

Table 6: Identified tree ornamental plants planted at roads at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences

Family name	Scientific name	English name	Common name
Combretaceae	<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	Umbrella tree, step tree	India almond
Fabaceae	<i>Delonix regia</i>	Flame of the forest	Bark cloth tree
Combretaceae	<i>Plumeria acutifolia</i>	Frangipani	Red-jasmine or temple tree
Fabaceae	<i>Pentaclethra macrophylla</i>	African oil bean	Ugba or Ukpaka
Arecaceae	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	African oil palm	African oil palm
Lamiaceae	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Beechwood	Gmelina
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Hura creptans</i>	Sandbox tree	Monkey no climb

Lamiaceae	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	Teak	Teak
Irvingiaceae	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	African mango	Bush mango
Rosaceae	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Almond tree	Fruit tree
Pinaceae	<i>Pinus densiflora</i>	Pinus	Japanese red pine
Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	neem tree	Margosa
Annonaceae	<i>Pllyalthia longifolia</i>	Masquerade	Police, False ashoka tree

Table 7: Ornamental plants identified at the Senate and Administrative Buildings at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo

Scientific name	Mode of identification (flowers, leaves and cones)	Mode of propagation	Uses
Ornamental plants			
<i>Duranta</i> spp.	Flowers are light-blue or lavender	Stem cutting	Hedges
<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	The colour of the flower is white or light red Green leaves with combination of other colours	Stem cutting	Focal plant Hedges, Focal and potted plant
<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i>	Flowers are yellow and funnel-shaped	Stem cutting	Hedges
<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	The flowers are red and tubular-shaped	Seed or stem cutting	Hedges
<i>Ixora coccinea</i>	Flowers are orange to red with tubular-shaped	Stem cutting	Hedges
<i>Hamelia patens</i>	leaves are deep green and lime green-yellow	Stem cuttings	Hedges, indoor decoration
<i>Ficus altissima</i>	White, yellow or red	Stem cutting	Focal plant and cut flower
<i>Rosa-sinensis</i>	The spores are on a light-brown cone	Stem cutting	Groundcover and screens
<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	Flowers are pink to purple in zigzag form	Spores	Focal plant
<i>Heliconia bourgaeana</i>	Flowers are yellow and trumpet-shaped	Rhizome	Covering fences
<i>Allamanda cathartica</i>	Flowers are white	Stem cutting	Indoor decoration
<i>Polyscias scutellaria</i>	Flowers are orange-red	Stem cutting	Hanging, indoor, focal plant
<i>Episcia cupreata</i>	Flowers are white and with fragrant smell	Stolon (runners)	Hedges
<i>Eugenia uniflora</i>	Flowers are yellow-green	Stem cutting	Indoor and potted plant
<i>Euphobia ammask</i>	Green leaves green with silver variegations.	Cuttings	Hedges
<i>Pseuderanthemum stainless</i>	White flower with coppery green leaves	Stem cuttings	Covering fences
<i>Philodendron hederaceum</i>	Flowers are orange-red	Stem cuttings	Cut flowers
<i>Hippeastrum puniceum</i>	Lance-shaped green leaves with silver blotches	Bulbs	Indoor decoration
Indoor plants			
<i>Aglaonema commutatum</i>	Oval-shaped leaves with white stripes at its edge	Cuttings	Hedges
<i>Polyscias scutellaria</i>	Heart-shaped leaves with colourfull patches	Stem cuttings	Indoor or potted plant
<i>Caladium bicolor</i>	Flowers are greenish-white with fragrant smell	Corm	Potted plant
<i>Sansevieria trifasciata</i>	Flowers are Cup-shaped with pink colour	Cuttings or sucker	Potted plant
<i>Jatropha integerrima</i>	Pinkish-orange to red flowers	Seed or cuttings	Potted plant
<i>Jatropha podagrica</i>		Seed or stem cuttings	

<i>Carex oshimensis</i>	Leaves are yellow with dark green margins Flowers are lilac-whitish purple in colour	Seeds	Bordures or mixed flower beds Indoor / potted plant
<i>Cordyline asparagus</i>		Stem cuttings	
Tree species			
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Flowers are star-shaped and white Resembles that of <i>C. sinensis</i>	Seed and grafting	Orchard, food and shade Orchards, food and shade
<i>Citrus japonica</i>	Flowers are white with a yellow flushed centre	Seeds and grafting	Focal plant and shade
<i>Plumeria acutifolia</i>	Purple or red flowers	Seeds or grafting	Orchard and Food
<i>Ananas comosus</i>	Yellowish flowers borne on inflorescences	Sucker	Plantation, food, avenue plant
<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	Flowers are white	Seed	Avenue plant and shades
<i>Leucaena Leucocephala</i>	Flowers are yellowish green	Seed, cuttings	Orchard and food
<i>Annona muricata</i>	Flowers clusters in inflorescence.	Seed, grafting	Food
<i>Cocos nucifera</i> (L.)	Yellowish-brown 5-lobed flower	Seed	Shade and avenue plant
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Fragrant white flowers arranged in clusters	Seeds and cuttings	Shades and avenue plant
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	Creamy white	Seeds and cuttings	Focal plant and avenue plant
<i>Archontophoenix alexandrae</i>	Inflorescence	Seeds	Food and shade plant
<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Bowl-shaped, pink or white fragrant flowers	Seed	
<i>Pinus densiflora</i>	Oval-shaped cones	Seeds or cuttings	Avenue plant, shade Focal plant and Avenue plant
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	Creamy-yellow flowers yellow to greenish-white	Seed	Plantation and food
<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	flowers	Seed	Avenue plant
<i>Delonix regia</i>	Scarlet or orange-red flowers	Seed	
<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	White to cream flowers	Seed and cuttings	Avenue plant
<i>Hura creptans</i>	Red flowers with no petals	Seed	Avenue plant, shade
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	white and fragrant flower	Seed, cutting	Avenue plant
<i>Carica papaya</i>	Funnel-shaped yellow flower,	Seed	Food
<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	six brown, yellow, or greenish flower	Seed	Focal plant and Avenue plant
<i>Magnifera indica</i>	yellow to pinkish white in colour	Seed, grafting	Food and shade
<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	Whitish green flowers with fragrant smell	Seed and grafting	Avenue plant and shade
<i>Pentaclethra macrophylla</i>	Fragrant and pale yellow flower	Seed	Plantation and Food

Table 8: Plantations and orchards within University of Agriculture and environmental Sciences, Umuagwo

Family	Scientific name	English name	Location	Type
Arecaceae	<i>Elaeis guinensis</i>	Oil palm	Love garden	Plantation
Bromliaceae	<i>Ananas comosus</i>	Pineapple	Faculty of Art	Orchard
Annonaceae	<i>Annona muricata</i>	Soursop	Senate building	Orchard
	<i>Pentaclethra</i>			Plantation
Fabaceae	<i>macrophylla</i>	African oil bean	Love garden	
Irvingiaceae	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	Bush mango	Otanmiri	Plantation

Conclusion

Fifty three ornamental plants and tree species were encountered within the UAES. Twenty three of them are tree species, 23 are outdoor ornamental plants and seven of them are indoor ornamental plants. They are mainly being used as hedges, screens, avenue plants, focal plants, shade plants. Their modes of propagation were mainly stem cuttings for ornamental plants and seeds, for tree species. This finding will provide information on the names and propagation of many of these ornamental plants and trees for easy identification and uses by florists, horticulturists and researchers. It is recommended that both public and private buildings and places be landscaped with trees and ornamental plants. This will not only add aesthetic value but also enhance the quality of the environment as plants act as carbon sink, windbreak and erosion control measures.

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